

Effect of Organised Surfactant System on the Kinetics of Acid-catalysed Hydrolysis of Ethyl Acetate

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Although hydrolysis of esters of very complex structure has been studied in presence of surfactants¹⁻⁴, but their effect on the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of very simple esters like ethyl acetate has not been examined. Hence the present study was undertaken to gather additional informations in the field of micellar chemistry.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in aqueous acid medium have been studied in absence and presence of varying concentrations of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), Triton-X-100 at 30°. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants are given in Table 1. The effects of temperature (25–40°), variation of concentration of ester, acid and electrolytes on the reaction rate in presence of surfactants have been presented in Tables 2–4.

The acid-catalysed hydrolysis involves proton transfer from the acid to an ester oxygen atom followed by the rate-determining cleavage of C–O bond forming an acyl carbonium ion intermediate which reacts with water to give carboxylic acid (Scheme 1).

In presence of surfactants beyond their critical micelle-concentration (CMC), the hydrolysis will occur both in micellar aggregates and in bulk phase.

Effect of cationic surfactant (CTAB) : The effect of varying concentration of CTAB above its CMC upon the first order rate constant (k_1) indicates that it decreases gradually upto 0.07 M [surfactant]. It happens for two reasons : (i) due to incorporation of ethyl acetate molecules into the micelles by

hydrophobic interaction and (ii) due to the hindrance of proton transfer to the ester molecules, which initiates the hydrolysis, by the electrostatic repulsion of positive head groups of the cationic micelle. Hence reaction will mainly take place in the bulk phase. The hydrolysis in surfactant medium can be explained

Scheme 1

by distribution model often used for enzymatic catalysis². The gradual decrease of the observed reaction rate on increasing [CTAB] is due to increase in the number of micellar aggregates which entrap more and more ester molecules causing the drop of [ester] in the bulk phase. Similar decrease in the rate of acid-catalysed hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenyl propionate in presence of cationic surfactant has been observed³.

Effect of anionic surfactant (NaLS) : In presence

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR ACIDCATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL ACETATE IN VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF SURFACTANTS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

[Ethyl acetate] = 0.204 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M,
Temp = 30°

[CTAB] (M)	0.00	0.002	0.005	0.008	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.07
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	7.66	6.71	6.39	6.26	6.14	5.87	5.60	5.20
	± 0.038	± 0.0037	± 0.032	± 0.031	± 0.03	± 0.032	± 0.027	± 0.03
[NaLS] (M)	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	7.66	8.22	8.44	8.95	9.59	9.98	10.23	9.59
	± 0.038	± 0.037	± 0.035	± 0.031	± 0.031	± 0.043	± 0.032	± 0.036
Temp. = 40°								
[Triton-X-100] ml/100 ml	0.00	0.80	1.0	1.4	2.0	—	—	—
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	16.61	15.35	15.35	15.35	15.35	—	—	—
	± 0.073	± 0.047	± 0.046	± 0.063	± 0.053			

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL ACETATE IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS

[Ethyl acetate] = 0.204 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M,
 $10^5 k_1$ (s⁻¹) at

	25°	30°	35°	40°	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{\ddagger a}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^{\ddagger a}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^{\ddagger a}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
[Surfactant] = 0.00 M								
6.30	7.66	12.21	16.61	52.70	50.18	151.67	96.14	
± 0.033	± 0.038	± 0.058	± 0.073	± 0.15	± 0.15	± 0.49	± 0.35	
[CTAB] = 0.02 M								
5.29	6.14	10.56	14.86	57.44	54.92	138.05	96.75	
± 0.039	± 0.03	± 0.053	± 0.073	± 0.18	± 0.18	± 0.59	± 0.35	
[NaLS] = 0.03 M								
7.67	8.95	13.43	19.19	50.36	47.84	158.14	95.76	
± 0.026	± 0.047	± 0.047	± 0.066	± 0.16	± 0.16	± 0.52	± 0.32	

^aAt 30°.

of NaLS the gradual hydrolytic rate enhancement has been observed upto 0.06 M [surfactant] followed by a decrease in rate on further increasing [NaLS]. This enhancement is due to the increased concentration of ester in the increased number of anionic micelles, availability of proton in the Stern layer and stabilisation of acyl carbonium ion for coulombic interaction. When all the ester molecules are solubilised in available micelles further increase of micellar moieties will cause rate retardation as availability of proton (H⁺ ion) will decrease in Stern layers. As ester solubilised in one micelle can not react with H⁺ (counter ion) present at the other micelle⁵. Sakurada *et al.*⁴ observed similar rate acceleration in acid-catalysed hydrolysis of some acetates.

The kinetic data in presence of NaLS were fitted to the equation derived from Menger-Portnoy dis-

tribution model². A plot of $1/(k_w - k_{obs})$ vs $1/(C_D - CMC)$ resulted a straight line upto 0.06 M NaLS.

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS OF ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL ACETATE AT VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF ESTER AND ACID IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS AT 30°

[HCl] = 0.45 M

[Ester]	$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)		
M	[Surfactant] = 0.00 M	[CTAB] = 0.02 M	[NaLS] = 0.03 M
0.204	7.66 ± 0.038	6.14 ± 0.03	8.95 ± 0.031
0.306	8.36 ± 0.035	6.90 ± 0.031	7.83 ± 0.037
0.408	11.12 ± 0.051	8.21 ± 0.046	7.32 ± 0.032
0.510	14.62 ± 0.035	9.59 ± 0.024	7.10 ± 0.04
[HCl]	[Ester] = 0.204 M		
M			
0.35	4.65 ± 0.051	2.95 ± 0.014	—
0.40	5.75 ± 0.026	5.10 ± 0.023	—
0.45	7.66 ± 0.038	6.14 ± 0.03	—
0.50	9.59 ± 0.05	6.90 ± 0.031	—
0.55	10.20 ± 0.044	9.59 ± 0.026	—

From the intercept and slope of the plot the values of binding constant (K) and k_m were found to be 6.71×10^2 and $14.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively, where k_{obs} , k_w and k_m are rate constants observed in water medium and in micellar phase respectively; $C_D = [\text{NaLS}]$ and aggregation number (N) for NaLS⁶ taken to be 62 for calculation.

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS OF ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL ACETATE IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS AT 30°

[Ethyl acetate] = 0.204 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M,
 $10^5 k_1$ (s^{-1}) at salt concentrations

Salt	0.00 M	0.40 M	0.50 M	0.60 M
In absence of surfactant				
NaCl	7.66 ± 0.038	7.13 ± 0.023	6.92 ± 0.028	6.71 ± 0.022
NaBr	7.66 ± 0.038	5.75 ± 0.023	5.75 ± 0.023	5.75 ± 0.024
In presence of 0.02 M CTAB				
NaCl	6.14 ± 0.03	4.60 ± 0.032	4.18 ± 0.019	3.83 ± 0.021
In presence of 0.03 M NaLS				
NaCl	8.95 ± 0.031	7.67 ± 0.029	7.32 ± 0.032	7.04 ± 0.033

Effect of nonionic surfactant (Triton-X-100) : The kinetic effect of Triton-X-100 was found to be negligible which may be due to very little micellar binding of the ester (Table 1). The effect in this study is similar to those reported earlier⁶.

Temperature effect : Thermodynamic quantities calculated for this hydrolysis in presence of CTAB and NaLS are given in Table 2. The higher and lower activation energy, enthalpy values for the reaction in presence of CTAB and NaLS respectively, indicate destabilisation and stabilisation of transition states in comparison to its stability in absence of surfactant, and must be due to different types of interactions. The values of entropy and free energy of activation follow similar trends. The high negative values of entropy suggest more ordering of the transition state and the trend depends on the mobility of the substrate in different environments.

Effect of substrate and acid concentrations : As expected⁷, in absence of surfactant at fixed [acid], the observed rate constant increased on increasing [ester] (Table 3). Under identical condition with 0.02 M CTAB and 0.03 M NaLS, enhancement and suppression in rates have been observed. With CTAB it is usual but with NaLS it may be due to saturation of anionic micellar phase with increasing

[substrate] as observed by other workers⁸. A fixed [ester] and varying [acid], rates have been found to show expected changes in absence and presence of 0.02 M CTAB. Under such conditions⁷, the rate will be proportional to $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$ and governed by Bronsted catalysis equation⁹.

Salt effect : With increasing amount of NaCl, the decrease in rate has been observed in absence and presence of CTAB and NaLS (Table 4). Although in such reaction in absence of surfactant 'salt-in' of ester will cause rate retardation and chloride ion will stabilise positive transition state relative to proton¹⁰, the net effect was retardation. In presence of NaLS, added salt decreased the rate due to reduction in micellar charge with an increase in the number of counter ions in the Stern layer and displacement of reactive species from micelles. With CTAB further rate suppression on addition of salt may be due to decrease in catalytic effect of proton for excess chloride ion. However, the effect of increasing concentration of NaBr on the rate was insignificant.

Experimental

CTAB and NaLS (both B.D.H.) were purified¹¹. Triton-X-100 (B.D.H.) was used as received. Baryta was prepared of barium hydroxide (E. Merck) by standard method and standardised. HCl and other salts were of reagent grade. Salts were dried before use. Ethyl acetate (E. Merck) was purified¹². Triple-distilled water was used for the preparation of solution and dilution.

Kinetic experiments carried out in a thermostat at the desired temperature in the usual way. Aliquots (5 ml) of the reaction mixture were quenched by adding crushed ice and the acid was estimated by baryta at regular time interval. Reading for infinite time was noted after 24 h.

The rate constant for the reaction was calculated using the expression,

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{V_\infty - V_0}{V_\infty - V_t},$$

where V_0 , V_t and V_∞ are titre values at zero time, after time t and infinite time respectively. The k and other related quantities were determined in the usual way.

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